

Reactivity of Benzoylperoxy Radicals with Monoterpenes: One-Step Reaction to Form Low-Volatility Organic Compounds

Dominika Pasik,* Noora Hyttinen, Siddharth Iyer, and Nanna Myllys*

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ABSTRACT: Oxidation of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) significantly impacts air quality and climate by contributing to ozone and secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation. Accurate representation of VOC oxidation in atmospheric models is essential but challenging due to complex reaction mechanisms. Using high-level computational tools, we investigate oxidation reactions of α -pinene, β -pinene, limonene, and sabinene, initiated by benzoyl peroxy radical. The calculated total reaction rate coefficients are on the order of 10^{-14} – 10^{-15} cm^3/s , which is fast enough to be competitive under clean, low- NO_x atmospheric conditions. Further oxidation pathways of sabinene-derived RO_2 were studied. We identified an oxidation pathway that propagates the oxidative chain and may help explain the high SOA yields observed for sabinene.

Moreover, saturation vapor pressures of benzoyl peroxy radical-initiated oxidation intermediates were estimated using the COSMOtherm program and a machine learning model (COSMO-ML). The results suggest that one of these intermediates is already a low-volatility organic compound (LVOC) with a saturation vapor pressure of 10^{-7} pascal. Furthermore, we find that later-generation oxidation products of sabinene have saturation vapor pressures low enough to classify them as extremely low-volatility organic compounds (ELVOC). These findings highlight a potentially important SOA formation route with significant atmospheric and environmental implications.

KEYWORDS: monoterpenes, acyl peroxy radicals, oxidation, VOCs, aerosols, LVOCs

1. INTRODUCTION

The Earth's atmosphere is a complex system, where innumerable reactions take place every second. Although its composition is dominated by nitrogen (N_2 , 78%) and oxygen (O_2 , 21%), the processes occurring within the remaining 1% of compounds are crucial.¹ These reactions involve intricate mechanisms with direct implications for air quality and the climate. Among them, the gas-phase chemistry of organic peroxy radicals (RO_2) is particularly significant.^{2–4} Their autoxidation has been identified as a key pathway leading to the formation of highly oxygenated organic molecules (HOMs).^{5–7} These compounds are commonly thought to have low volatilities, which enable their condensing onto existing particles and contributing to aerosol formation and growth.^{8–13} Atmospheric aerosols play a major role in the Earth's climate system by scattering solar radiation, modifying cloud properties, thus affecting the Earth's radiation balance and climate.^{14–17} Additionally, they impact human health.^{18,19} Despite significant progress, the complexity and vastness of volatile organic compounds (VOC)-derived RO_2 chemistry leave much yet to be explored.²⁰ Understanding the mechanisms leading to HOMs, and consequently to organic

aerosols, is of critical importance for global atmospheric models and the environment.

Volatility is a key property that determines whether an organic compound remains in the gas phase or can partition to form particles. Compounds with extremely low volatilities can contribute to initial particle growth.²¹ However, this process is influenced not only by volatility itself but also by molecular structure, functional groups, and atmospheric conditions. Despite substantial efforts, the chemical structures of many compounds involved in aerosol processes remain poorly characterized.¹¹ Experimental techniques and group-contribution models alone are insufficient to fully resolve this complexity. Therefore, quantum chemistry-based methods are essential to complement existing approaches and improve our understanding of atmospheric oxidation products.

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Saturation vapor pressure allows for classifying organic compounds into groups (volatile organic compounds (VOCs), semivolatile organic compounds (SVOCs), low-volatility organic compounds (LVOCs), extremely low-volatility organic compounds (ELVOCs), ultralow-volatility organic compounds (ULVOCs)) and assessing their role in secondary organic aerosol (SOA) formation.^{22–24} ULVOCs ($p_{\text{sat}} < 10^{-14}$ Pa) can initiate SOA formation, ELVOCs ($p_{\text{sat}} < 10^{-8}$ Pa) condense almost irreversibly onto particles, driving new particle formation and growth in the atmosphere,²⁵ while SVOCs ($p_{\text{sat}} < 10^{-2}$ Pa) and LVOCs ($p_{\text{sat}} < 10^{-6}$ Pa) contribute mainly to aerosol's growth.^{9,26–29} Typically, compounds with approximately 15 carbon atoms and multiple oxygen-containing functional groups exhibit low saturation vapor pressures and thus fall into the low-volatility regime.³⁰ Therefore, estimation of saturation vapor pressure helps predict compound's role in SOA formation.

RO_2 radicals are formed in the atmosphere through the oxidation of VOCs, primarily initiated by the OH radical, NO_3 radical, and ozone.^{23,31–34} Another oxidant is the Cl radical, which accounts for the oxidation of nonmethane alkenes, aromatics, and aldehydes, among others, in the lower troposphere. It also contributes to ozone production.^{35–37}

Among biogenic sources, monoterpenes ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$) constitute the second-largest fraction of emitted nonmethane VOCs and are major contributors to the formation of SOA.^{38–40} Their oxidation reactions are the subject of numerous theoretical and experimental studies, which focus on unraveling the autoxidation mechanisms that drive the formation of low-volatile organic compounds.^{8,11,22,32,41–44} On the other hand, human activities, such as combustion processes, lead to anthropogenic emissions of various compounds, including aromatics and carbonyl compounds.^{45–48} Among them, benzaldehyde is released into the atmosphere from fuel combustion and solvent use processes.^{49–51} It can also form in situ through the OH-initiated oxidation of aromatic hydrocarbons (mainly toluene). Benzaldehyde concentrations in the atmosphere vary depending on the location and are typically observed at higher levels in polluted areas with significant vehicle emissions.⁵⁰ Villanueva et al.⁵² reported benzaldehyde concentrations around $0.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Cabañeros National Park in the central-southern Iberian Peninsula, Spain; Baptista et al.⁵³ reported values of $0.2 (\pm 0.07) \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for the city of Córdoba, Argentina; Braga et al.⁵⁴ measured the levels of benzaldehyde in the Metropolitan Region of Rio de Janeiro to be in the range of 0.11 – $5.99 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Ait Taleb et al.⁵⁵ observed high levels of benzaldehyde (mean 4.9 – $9.2 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, maximum $23.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) in industrial sites in Morocco. These values correspond to around 10^9 – 10^{11} molecules cm^{-3} of benzaldehyde in the atmosphere. Benzaldehyde was also detected in residential indoor air (at levels of 0.1 – 1 ppb in Helsinki, Finland; Boston, USA; and New Jersey, USA).^{56,57} The initial steps of benzaldehyde oxidation include the attack of an OH radical (or Cl atom), leading to the formation of the benzoyl radical, which can subsequently react with O_2 to form the benzoyl peroxy radical.^{49,58,59} Further reactions of this compound most likely include bimolecular reactions, for example, with HO_2 or reactions with other RO_2 , leading to the formation of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{O})\text{O}$. Experimental studies by Strollo and Ziemann (2016) demonstrated that the bimolecular self-reaction of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$ to form cyclic tetraoxide intermediates (ROOOO) has less than 0.1% yield.⁴⁹ However, to the best of our knowledge, only a few studies

have addressed the topic of benzaldehyde oxidation.^{49–51,58,60,61}

The benzoyl peroxy radical can be classified as an acyl peroxy radical (APR). This class of radicals possesses the $\text{R}-\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}$ functional group. APRs are known to be highly reactive, with short lifetimes in the atmosphere.^{62,63} They can undergo bimolecular reactions with NO_2 to form peroxyacyl nitrates (PANs) or unimolecular reactions via H-shifts.^{64–68} However, recent studies by Karppinen et al. (2025)⁶⁹ have shown that the benzoyl peroxy radical exhibits slow unimolecular reaction rates, making it a strong candidate for bimolecular reactions. Moreover, Pasik et al. (2024)⁷⁰ demonstrated that APRs can react with unsaturated hydrocarbons by adding to the double bond, with reaction rate coefficients on the order of $10^{-15} \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$. In that paper, the reaction of isoprene with various peroxy radicals was tested, among which the benzoyl peroxy radical gave the lowest energy barriers for the accretion reaction.⁷⁰ For these reasons, the focus of this study is the benzoyl peroxy radical-initiated oxidation of four atmospherically relevant monoterpenes: α -pinene, β -pinene, limonene, and sabinene (see Figure 1). This

Figure 1. Structures of the investigated monoterpenes. The positions of benzoyl peroxy radical addition to double bonds are marked with numbers. The numbers on the figure correspond to the numbering in Table 1.

research aims to assess the impact of monoterpene oxidation initiated by APR, especially in the context of low-volatility compound formation, as they can contribute to aerosol formation and growth.

2. METHODS

2.1. Computational Details. To evaluate the mechanisms and rates of monoterpene oxidation by the benzoyl peroxy radical, we calculated the reaction energy barrier for the accretion reaction, as well as subsequent ring-opening, H-shift, and endocyclization reactions, using quantum chemistry methods. To do this, we optimized the structures of reactants and products using density functional theory (DFT) at the $\omega\text{B97X-D}/6-31+\text{G}^*$ level of theory.^{71–74} Corresponding transition states (TS) were located from the relaxed potential energy surface scan at the same level of theory. These structures were then used as input for conformational sampling to find the global minima structure, which was carried out using the Conformer–Rotamer Ensemble Sampling Tool (CREST) software at the GFN2-xTB level.^{75,76} The number of obtained conformers was first reduced with respect to xTB energy using $2.5 \text{ kcal}/\text{mol}$ as a cutoff and further optimized at the $\omega\text{B97X-D}/6-31+\text{G}^*$ level. Conformers of transition state (TS) structures were first optimized with constrained forming/breaking bond distances, followed by full TS geometry optimization and frequency calculation. Transition states were verified by the presence of exactly one imaginary frequency. For conformers of reactants and products, direct

Table 1. Zero-Point Corrected Energies [Kcal/Mol] for Monoterpene + C₆H₅C(O)OO· accretion reaction barrier (ΔE) was calculated at the DLPNO-CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ// ω B97X-D/6-31+G⁴**

monoterpene	ΔE	k_{TST}	k_{total}	$k_{\text{pseudo}} [\text{APR}]$	$k_{\text{pseudo}} [\text{OH}]$	$k_{\text{pseudo}} [\text{NO}_3]$	$k_{\text{pseudo}} [\text{O}_3]$
α -Pinene-1 (a)	-0.6	1.9×10^{-15}	2.0×10^{-15}	2.0×10^{-7}	5.3×10^{-5}	1.5×10^{-3}	6.3×10^{-5}
α -Pinene-2 (a)	1.5	4.7×10^{-17}					
α -Pinene-1 (b)	2.7	1.3×10^{-17}					
α -Pinene-2 (b)	4.5	9.8×10^{-20}					
β -Pinene-1 (a)	0.1	5.9×10^{-16}	6.5×10^{-16}	6.3×10^{-8}	9.3×10^{-5}	5.2×10^{-4}	1.1×10^{-5}
β -Pinene-2 (a)	2.8	6.0×10^{-18}					
β -Pinene-1 (b)	1.8	5.1×10^{-17}					
β -Pinene-2 (b)	5.2	4.0×10^{-20}					
Sabinene-1 (a)	-1.9	1.5×10^{-15}	3.1×10^{-15}	3.1×10^{-7}	1.1×10^{-4}	2.5×10^{-3}	5.6×10^{-5}
Sabinene-2 (a)	1.2	6.5×10^{-17}					
Sabinene-1 (b)	-0.3	1.5×10^{-15}					
Sabinene-2 (b)	3.3	5.0×10^{-18}					
Limonene-1 (a)	-1.2	1.3×10^{-15}	9.4×10^{-15}	9.4×10^{-7}	1.0×10^{-4}	3.0×10^{-3}	2.3×10^{-4}
Limonene-2 (a)	-0.8	1.6×10^{-15}					
Limonene-3	2.6	1.1×10^{-17}					
Limonene-4	-0.1	3.2×10^{-16}					
Limonene-1 (b)	-0.5	8.6×10^{-16}					
Limonene-2 (b)	-0.9	5.0×10^{-15}					

⁴The corresponding reaction rate coefficients were calculated at 298 K for monoterpene + C₆H₅C(O)OO· accretion reaction (k_{TST}) [$\text{cm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] was calculated using the MC-TST equation. The total reaction rate coefficient was calculated as the sum of all four (for α -pinene, β -pinene, and sabinene) or six (for limonene) reaction rate coefficients. Pseudounimolecular Reaction Rate coefficients (k_{pseudo}) [s^{-1}] were compared with competing OH-addition, NO₃-addition, and O₃-addition experimental data.⁹⁷⁻¹⁰⁰ Concentrations of reactants used to calculate reaction rates were: [C₆H₅C(O)OO·] = $1 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, [OH] = $1 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, [NO₃] = $2.5 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and [O₃] = $7 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Reported rates carry an uncertainty of about a factor of 5.

optimization and frequency calculations were performed. Based on electronic energy, dipole moment, and squared rotational constant values, duplicate structures were removed, and only unique conformers were considered in the final conformer sets.

To calculate the reaction energy barrier more accurately, on top of the DFT structures, linear-scaling coupled-cluster with single and double excitations, as well as perturbative inclusion of triples single-point calculations, were performed using the DLPNO-CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ method.⁷⁷⁻⁷⁹ The barrier heights were computed as the difference between the electronic energies, including zero-point vibrational corrections ($E_{\text{el}} + \text{ZPVE}$), of the lowest-energy conformers of the transition states and those of the reactants.

The reaction rate coefficients were calculated using the multiconformer transition state theory (MC-TST) approach for bimolecular reactions with the following expression:^{80,81}

$$k_{\text{bi}} = \kappa_t \frac{k_{\text{B}}T}{hP_{\text{ref}}Q_{\text{MT}}} \frac{\sum_i^{\text{allTScnf.}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_i}{k_{\text{B}}T}\right) Q_{\text{TS},i}}{\sum_j^{\text{allRconf.}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_j}{k_{\text{B}}T}\right) Q_{\text{R},j}} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{TS}} - E_{\text{R}}}{k_{\text{B}}T}\right) \quad (1)$$

where κ_t is the quantum-mechanical tunneling coefficient ($\kappa_t = 1$ is used for the reactions involving atoms other than hydrogen), T is the temperature (=298.15 K), h is the Planck's constant, P_{ref} is the reference pressure (=1 atm; here, we used the value $2.45 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and k_{B} is the Boltzmann's constant. $Q_{\text{R},j}$ and $Q_{\text{TS},i}$ are the partition functions of the reactant (benzoyl peroxy radical) and transition state conformers, respectively. Q_{MT} is the partition function of the monoterpene. ΔE_j and ΔE_i correspond to the zero-point

corrected electronic energies of the reactant and transition state conformers relative to the lowest-energy conformers, respectively. E_{R} and E_{TS} are the zero-point corrected electronic energies of the lowest-energy reactant and transition state conformers. The partition functions were calculated at the ω B97X-D/6-31+G* level of theory, while the reaction barrier ($E_{\text{TS}} - E_{\text{R}}$) includes the DLPNO-CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ energy correction.

For all unimolecular reactions (the hydrogen shift, ring-opening, and endocyclization reactions), the unimolecular reaction rate coefficients were calculated using the equation:⁸²

$$k_{\text{uni}} = \kappa_t \frac{k_{\text{B}}T}{h} \frac{\sum_i^{\text{allTScnf.}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_i}{k_{\text{B}}T}\right) Q_{\text{TS},i}}{\sum_j^{\text{allRconf.}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta E_j}{k_{\text{B}}T}\right) Q_{\text{R},j}} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{TS}} - E_{\text{R}}}{k_{\text{B}}T}\right) \quad (2)$$

The tunneling coefficient κ_t was calculated using the Eckart tunneling method, which estimated the tunneling factor based on the TS energy and energies of the reactant and product connected to that TS structure. Reactant and product conformers were taken from Intrinsic Reaction Coordinate (IRC) calculations and optimized at the ω B97X-D/6-31+G* level of theory. The forward and reverse barriers were calculated after the DLPNO-CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ energy corrections. It can be noted that eqs 1 and 2 differ only in reference pressure (P_{ref}) for unit conversion. DFT calculations were carried out using Gaussian 16 RevC.02 software.⁸³ single point energies were calculated using ORCA version 5.0.3.⁸⁴

The reaction kinetics for the sabinene alkyl radical ring-opening rearrangement were simulated using the Master Equation Solver for Multi Energy-well Reactions (MESMER) software⁸⁵ following the procedure described in Draper et al. (2024)⁸⁶ and our previous study.⁸⁷ Vibrational frequencies and

Figure 2. Structures of accretion reaction products, where the addition side was considered. Labeling on the figure corresponds to the labeling in Table 1.

rotational constants for all species of interest were calculated at the DFT level, while zero-point corrected energies were obtained at the DLPNO-CCSD(T)/aug-cc-pVTZ// ω B97X-D/6-31+G* level. Sabinene+APR-addition reaction was simulated using the Mesmer Inverse Laplace Transform (MesmerILT) method, assuming a barrierless association and using realistic bimolecular rate coefficients calculated in this work (k_{TST} was used as a pre-exponential factor in ILT reactions; see Table 1). The ring-break reactions were modeled using simple Rice-Ramsperger-Kassel-Marcus (RRKM) theory with an Eckart tunneling correction. O_2 -addition reactions for both sabinene+APR (R-APR) and ring-opened sabinene+APR (ring-opened R-APR) alkyl radicals were treated as bimolecular sinks in MESMER calculations. Bimolecular rate coefficients used were $6 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molecule}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for O_2 addition, with O_2 concentration of $5.16 \times 10^{18} \text{ molecules cm}^{-3}$ (0.21 atm), as used in previous studies.^{42,86,87} Parameters used for the simulations were as follows: N_2 was used as the bath gas with Lennard-Jones parameters $\epsilon/k_{\text{B}} = 91.85 \text{ K}$ and $\sigma = 3.919 \text{ \AA}$; the exponential-down parameter $\Delta E_{\text{down}} = 225 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; grain size was 30 cm^{-1} ; and the energy span above the highest-energy transition state was $50 k_{\text{B}}T$. The high $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}$ -concentration used was $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to ensure the formation of the sabinene+APR (R-APR) adduct. The Lennard-Jones parameter values were estimated based on Joback and Reid (1987)⁸⁸ and are provided in Supplement Section 7.^{85,89}

2.2. Saturation Vapor Pressure Calculations. We used two different conductor-like screening model (COSMO; Schäfer et al., 2000)⁹⁰ based methods to calculate saturation vapor pressures of the oxidation products and intermediate radicals. Conductor-like screening model for real solvents

(COSMO-RS; Klamt, 1995;⁹¹ Klamt et al., 1998;⁹² Eckert and Klamt, 2002)⁹³ utilizes statistical thermodynamics, while COSMO-ML⁹⁴ uses a combination of COSMO-quantum chemical calculations and machine learning for saturation vapor pressure predictions.

Conformer sets from CREST conformer search were used as input in COSMO calculations with the COSMOconf program.⁹⁵ The geometries of all unique conformers were first optimized at the BP/SV(P)-COSMO level of theory. After duplicate conformers were removed, final geometries were obtained at the BP/TZVP-COSMO level of theory, with single-point energies calculated at the BP/TZVPD-FINE-COSMO level of theory. The gas-phase geometries and energies were calculated using the corresponding gas-phase calculation methods (BP/TZVP-GAS and BP/TZVPD-GAS, respectively).

COSMO-RS calculations were performed with the COSMOtherm program⁹⁶ and BP_TZVPD_FINE_24 parametrization. For the calculations, we selected the 10 conformers with the lowest condensed-phase free energies (pure compound) and gas-phase energies. However, condensed-phase conformers with high chemical potential were omitted to avoid the overestimation of the effect of intramolecular hydrogen bonds on COSMO energies.⁹⁴ For the COSMO-ML calculations, we used a single lowest condensed-phase free energy conformer, following the selection of the conformers in the training data of the COSMO-ML model by Hyttinen et al. (2024).⁹⁴ With the COSMO-ML model, we predicted saturation vapor pressures assuming both liquid and solid-state pure compounds.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Addition of $C_6H_5C(O)OO\cdot$ to Double Bond. In the first step, we investigate the addition reaction of the benzoyl peroxy radical to the double bond in monoterpene structures. Based on our previous studies,⁸⁷ we can already anticipate which position in the monoterpene will be most favored; however, we consider all possible sides to calculate the total reaction rate coefficients for the reactions of interest. Moreover, we highlighted the importance of including stereochemistry when investigating additions of acyl peroxy radicals to double bonds in monoterpenes.⁸⁷ According to our results, the addition of a peroxy radical to the double bond in α -pinene can occur in four different ways: first, there are two double-bond carbons where the radical can add, and second, there are two distinct sides of addition on each carbon atom. This leads to differences in the calculated reaction barriers and rate coefficients, depending on whether the addition occurs at the cyclobutyl ring side or the methyl group side in α -pinene.

To correctly assess the significance of the investigated reactions, we also considered both possible sides of APR addition in our study. Figure 2 presents the products of the addition of benzoyl peroxy radical to monoterpenes. Calculated accretion reaction barrier heights (ΔE) with corresponding reaction rate coefficients (k_{TST}) are listed in Table 1.

We indeed observe differences in the calculated barriers for different sides of the benzoyl peroxy radical attack. For example, in the case of sabinene, depending on the addition side, the calculated barriers differ by approximately 1.6 kcal/mol, resulting in an almost one-order-of-magnitude difference in the calculated reaction rate coefficients. For both α -pinene and β -pinene, we observe that addition at the cyclobutyl ring side (marked with “a”) is faster than at the methyl group side (marked with “b”), which is consistent with our previous findings for α -pinene.⁸⁷ In the case of sabinene, the fastest addition also occurs on the secondary ring side. For all studied monoterpenes, the fastest reaction pathway involves the formation of a tertiary radical.

For limonene, surprisingly, we observe the lowest barrier for the addition reaction leading to the formation of a secondary radical (system marked as limonene-1 (a)). However, the fastest rate occurs for limonene-2 (b), which results in tertiary radical formation. In the case of addition to the exocyclic double bond (positions 3 and 4), due to the rotation of the C–C bond, we assume that the barriers for both addition sides are equal. For this reason, the k_{total} includes the rate coefficients calculated for limonene-3 and limonene-4, each multiplied by two. It should be noted that for some reactions, the calculated energy barriers are negative. This is common for addition reactions of radicals, which often proceed via prereactive complexes. Barriers relative to these complexes are provided in the (Supplement Table S6). Importantly, calculated Gibbs free energy barriers are all positive, and the corresponding reaction rate coefficients are consistent with those obtained using MC-TST. Further details are given in Supplement, Section S7.

We calculated the total reaction rate coefficients for the accretion reaction for each monoterpene and compared them with experimental data for OH, NO_3 and ozone oxidation to assess how competitive these reactions are. The average concentration of OH radicals in the atmosphere is approximately 10^6 molecules/cm³,^{101–103} while the atmospheric concentration of benzoyl peroxy radicals is not well

established. However, the concentration of acyl peroxy radicals has been shown to be around 2 orders of magnitude higher than OH (10^8 molecules/cm³).⁶² Based on benzaldehyde concentration measurements in ambient air, we can estimate the concentration of benzoyl peroxy radical; however, we emphasize that this value is highly location-specific. As mentioned in the Introduction, high benzaldehyde concentrations in urban/industrial areas can reach around 1–5 ppb. Using steady-state theory, we estimated benzoyl peroxy radical concentration to be around 10^7 – 10^8 molecules/cm³ (in high benzaldehyde, low NO_x conditions, more detailed analysis is provided in the Supplement, Section 8). Assuming the upper limit as the concentration of benzoyl peroxy radicals, we can calculate pseudo-first-order reaction rate coefficients for OH, ozone, NO_3 and APR addition reactions and directly compare them.

The results in Table 1 show that, in the upper-limit-case scenario, benzoyl peroxy radical-initiated oxidation would correspond to 1% of OH-initiated oxidation of the investigated monoterpenes. While this is a small value, these reactions, which combine accretion and oxidation reactions, might have a surprisingly important role in the production of low-volatility compounds in the atmosphere, as it was recently shown by Dada et al. (2023)³⁰ that highly oxygenated compounds with more than 15 carbon atoms can nucleate under atmospheric conditions. Recent studies by Karppinen et al. (2025)⁶⁹ investigated the temperature dependence of the reactions of isoprene with APRs and OH. According to this work, OH oxidation exhibits a negative temperature dependence, whereas APR oxidation shows a positive one. This implies that APR-initiated oxidation becomes more competitive at higher temperatures. Key unknowns that need to be addressed are the exact reaction rate coefficients for the investigated reactions. To the best of our knowledge, there are no experimental values for the investigated reactions between acyl peroxy radicals and monoterpenes. However, according to an experimental study by Nozière and Fache (2021),⁶³ the reaction between isoprene and $CH_3C(O)OO\cdot$ proceeds with a rate on the order of 10^{-14} molecules/cm³/s. This value is around 2 orders of magnitude faster than theoretical calculations from our previous study⁷⁰ where the calculated rate was $k_{bi} = 4.4 \times 10^{-16}$ molecules/cm³/s. This would imply that our calculations might underestimate the actual rates, and experimental rate measurements are still needed to validate these predictions. In the same study⁶³ the authors report SAR predictions for the reaction of $CH_3C(O)OO\cdot$ with limonene and α -pinene, which are in good agreement with rates reported by us,⁷⁰ but 1 to 2 orders of magnitude lower than experimental rates. The reaction rate coefficients reported in the present study are associated with an estimated uncertainty of approximately a factor of 5 (based on sensitivity analysis). Nevertheless, even when this error margin is considered, our calculated values remain slower than the available experimental data. Reconciling with the experimental values would require the computed barriers to be lower by approximately 1.5–2 kcal/mol. The approximations in the DLPNO–CCSD(T) approach could introduce uncertainties larger than those in canonical CCSD(T) for these reactions. However, performing canonical CCSD(T) is prohibitively expensive for these large systems. This highlights uncertainties in the estimation of absolute rate coefficients. Theoretical investigations serve as guidance, but experimental rate measurements are still needed to validate these predictions.

Figure 3. Studied reactions for sabinene+ benzoyl peroxy radical. Blue values indicate branching ratios obtained from the RRKM simulations. Standard deviations ($+\sigma/-\sigma$) were calculated from the logit-transformed distribution of branching ratios.

Figure 4. Energy diagram for the oxidation pathway of sabinene with the benzoyl peroxy radical. The energies of the reagents were calculated relative to the sum of the reactants. Relative energies are reported in kcal/mol. Abbreviations: R – reactants, RC – reaction complex, TS1 – transition state for the addition reaction, P – addition reaction product, TS2 – transition state for ring opening, R-O P – ring-opened product.

Reactions between APRs and monoterpenes might be highly relevant to experimental studies. In our recent work, we showed that accretion products of APR and alkenes were indeed observed in flow-tube CIMS experiments.^{70,104} The same studies showed subsequent ROOR dimer formation from the RO_2+RO_2 recombination pathway. This implies that, if similar recombination occurs under atmospheric conditions, APR-initiated oxidation can produce dimers with high molar mass and the potential to contribute to aerosol processes.

3.2. Alkyl Radical Ring-Opening Reaction for Sabinene. After the initial addition of the benzyl peroxy radical to a monoterpene, a carbon-centered radical is formed. The radical center is located near the secondary ring structure in α -pinene, β -pinene, and sabinene. Moreover, the accretion reaction leads to the release of excess energy, which has been shown in previous studies to be sufficient to open the secondary ring in some monoterpene structures.^{42,86,87} In Pasik et al. (2025),⁸⁷ we investigated the ring-opening reaction of five monoterpenes initiated by the acetyl peroxy radical ($CH_3C(O)OO\cdot$) and found the highest yield of ring-opening reaction for sabinene (31%). For α -pinene and β -pinene, the ring-opening yield was negligible (0–2%). For this reason, we investigated the ring-opening rearrangement only for sabinene. The question of interest is whether the benzoyl peroxy radical would lead to a similar or higher yield of the ring-opening reaction compared to the acetyl peroxy radical.

Figure 3 presents the structures of the studied systems, and Figure 4 presents reaction energetics. RRKM calculations show that approximately 36% of the sabinene + benzyl peroxy radical adduct undergoes a ring-opening reaction, while the remaining 64% undergoes direct O_2 addition. The former reaction is particularly important, as the ring-opened system is less strained and can promote more efficient autoxidation, leading to higher molecular functionalization. The uncertainty in this simulation was estimated as the standard deviation (σ) of the logit-transformed branching ratio distribution, yielding +55% and –33%. A similar error range was reported by Draper et al. (2024)⁸⁶ in their monoterpene+ NO_3 studies.

It is worth noting that, besides the ring-opening and O_2 -addition pathways, decomposition of the sabinene+APR (R-APR) adduct to form RO and an epoxide is also possible. However, branching between these two reactions is highly temperature-dependent. Under combustion temperatures ($T > 360$ K), epoxide formation is the sole product channel,¹⁰⁵ whereas at room temperature, epoxidation is kinetically limited, as demonstrated by the experimental work of Nozière et al. (2023)¹⁰⁶ and the theoretical study of Pasik et al. (2024).⁷⁰ Compared to the 31% ring-opening yield observed in the case of $CH_3C(O)OO\cdot$ -initiated oxidation, the yield for the $C_6H_5C(O)OO\cdot$ reaction is slightly higher at 36%. This modest increase in ring-opening yield for the benzoyl peroxy radical may be attributed to reaction energetics, as the excess

Figure 5. Proposed fate of sabinene + $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$. (and also $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$). Pathways in the dashed box were taken from Pasik et al. (2025)⁸⁷ reactions outside the box were calculated in this study. ΔE values are energy barrier heights in kcal/mol, k values are reaction rate coefficients in s^{-1} .

energy is approximately 3 kcal/mol higher, which promotes the ring-opening process (excess energy was 14.5 kcal/mol for $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$ and 17.7 kcal/mol for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$). In the paper by Draper et al. (2024),⁸⁶ the NO_3 -initiated oxidation followed by the ring-opening reaction was studied, showing an 86% yield for the sabinene ring-opened intermediate. The excess energy in that case was 23 kcal/mol. This differs from OH oxidation of sabinene, where Wang and Wang (2018)¹⁰⁷ reported an almost 100% ring-opening yield for the sabinene + OH adduct. It is worth noting that the RRKM-ME calculations consider only the lowest energy conformers of the stationary points along the potential energy surface (PES). This tends to overestimate the rate coefficients compared to those of the MC-TST method. However, here we focus on branching ratios, for which uncertainty analysis was conducted.

3.3. Sabinene Oxidation Mechanism. Furthermore, we focus on subsequent reactions that may occur for sabinene- and benzoyl-derived radicals. As the ring-opening reaction yield is non-negligible, we consider pathways for both ring-opened and ring-retaining peroxy radicals. First oxidation steps were already considered in our previous studies with the acetyl peroxy radical.⁸⁷ We continue this work here, aiming to identify potential low-volatility products. As shown in Pasik et al. (2025),⁸⁷ sabinene possesses diverse oxidation pathways (see Figure 5). The β -scission reactions for sabinene-alkoxy radicals are competitive and depend on the alkoxy-stereoisomer formed. We continue subsequent oxidation steps for sabinene + $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$ -derived radicals, assuming that analogous benzoyl peroxy-derived systems would react the same way. The reason for this is that benzoyl-peroxy-derived

systems considered are large and lead to high computational costs. For systems in which modifications of the initial APR were thought likely to impact the outcome, calculations were performed using the benzoyl peroxy radical. Reactions considered in this study are depicted in Figure 5.

According to the RRKM-ME calculations, two-thirds of sabinene undergo oxidation without a ring opening. Next steps include oxygen addition and formation of the alkoxy radical. Subsequently, sabinene-derived RO undergoes two competitive β -scission reactions, one of which leads to the termination of the oxidation pathway and the formation of a closed-shell sabinaketone, while the other leads to the formation of a carbon-centered radical. The branching ratio for these reactions depends on the stereoisomer. 70% of the R-alkoxy isomer undergoes a reaction leading to a closed-shell product, while the S-alkoxy isomer prefers β -scission with a yield of 71%. Details of these calculations are provided in Supplement Section 1.

Following the pathway that forms a carbon-centered radical and assuming further oxidation, the formed RO_2 undergoes a fast H-shift reaction that results in another carbon-centered radical marked here as RC1 (see Figure 5). The addition of oxygen to carbon-centered radicals is assumed to be very fast and proceeds at a rate around 10^7 s^{-1} . However, the RC1 system has a radical center next to the 3-membered ring. Small rings are known to be very strained and thus prone to breaking. Calculations show that a ring-opening reaction for the RC1 system has a low barrier (1.8 kcal/mol), leading to a high reaction rate coefficient ($6 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$) that would outcompete O_2 addition. Interestingly, we found that the analogous

compound derived from the NO₃-initiated oxidation reacts similarly. Details of these calculations are provided in Supplement Section 5. This suggests a general rule: when the radical center is placed in the 3-membered ring, a ring-opening rearrangement is likely to occur.

Ring-opening reaction leads to the formation of a system with a new double bond (IM3). Further O₂-addition and unimolecular reactions of IM4 were considered and are presented schematically in Figure 6a. Corresponding reaction

Figure 6. Labeling for H-shift and endocyclization reactions of sabinene peroxy radicals IM4 and IM7. The numbers on the schemes correspond to the numberings in Table 2 for IM4 and Table 3 for IM7.

Table 2. Energy Barrier Heights [kcal/mol], Eckart Tunneling Factors (κ_t) and Calculated MC-TST Reaction Rate Coefficients [$k_{\text{MC-TST}}$ in s⁻¹ at 298 K] for the Studied Unimolecular Reactions of the Sabinene-Derived Peroxy Radical (IM4)^a

pathway	Barrier	$k_{\text{MC-TST}}$	κ_t
H-shift-1	28.0	2×10^{-5}	895
H-shift-2	17.9	8	80
H-shift-3	24.8	1×10^{-3}	414
H-shift-4	20.4	7×10^{-3}	23
Endo-5	12.1	1×10^3	-
Endo-6	13.9	3×10^1	-

^aReported rates carry an uncertainty of about a factor of 5.

rate coefficients are listed in Table 2. The results indicate that, among all tested unimolecular reactions, the fastest is endocyclization, which proceeds with a rate 10^3 s⁻¹ and leads to the formation of a five-membered ring (endo-5). This allows for the subsequent addition of aqueous O₂ and promotes the autoxidation process. Other reactions, such as a 6-membered ring formation or the 1,7-H-shift (marked here as H-shift-2), are also fast and possible.

Another pathway leads through the ring-opening reaction following the initial acetyl peroxy radical addition, which 31% of the radicals undergo. As a result, a carbon-centered radical is formed, which adds O₂ forming a peroxy radical RO₂ (denoted as RC2). For this system, H-shift reactions were considered in Pasik et al. (2025),⁸⁷ among which the fastest reaction proceeded with a rate of 10^{-2} s⁻¹ forming a resonance-stabilized radical denoted here as RC3 (see Figure 5). For this system, we calculate further oxidation pathways. In the first step, oxygen adds to the radical center, forming a peroxy radical marked as IM7. Subsequently, unimolecular H-shift and endocyclization reactions were considered for this system (see Figure 6b).

As shown in Table 3, the fastest reaction is H-shift-3, with a barrier of 23.8 kcal/mol and a reaction rate coefficient of $2 \times$

Table 3. Energy Barrier Heights [kcal/mol], Eckart Tunneling Factors (κ_t), and Calculated MC-TST Reaction Rate Coefficients [$k_{\text{MC-TST}}$ in s⁻¹ at 298 K] for the Studied Unimolecular Reactions of the Sabinene-Derived Peroxy Radical (IM7)^a

pathway	barrier	$k_{\text{MC-TST}}$	κ_t
H-shift-1	29.2	2×10^{-6}	4272
Endo-2	38.0	5×10^{-16}	-
H-shift-3	23.8	2×10^{-3}	536

^aReported rates carry an uncertainty of about a factor of 5.

10^{-3} s⁻¹. However, this reaction leads to the formation of the α -QOOR radical, which rapidly decomposes. This was observed in both intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) calculations and geometry optimization of the product. Therefore, for the tunneling coefficient calculations, we used the electronic energies obtained from the IRC path for the product structure (before decomposition). Based on these values, the calculated tunneling factor for H-shift-3 was 536, which was included in the MC-TST equation. We also applied the same method to calculate the tunneling factor for H-shift-1 to evaluate the difference between our approximated results and those that include zero-point energy corrections. The tunneling factor calculated from the electronic energy along the IRC path to the product structure prior to decomposition was 10,436 for H-shift-1, which is approximately twice the value obtained when zero-point energy corrections are included (4272). This implies that there is some uncertainty associated with these results. However, for the sabinene-derived RO₂ species investigated in this study, this approximation is sufficient, as it does not affect the overall conclusions that all unimolecular reactions are slow. A more detailed analysis is provided in Supplement Section 2.

3.4. Saturation Vapor Pressures. In this study, reactions between monoterpenes (C10) and the benzoyl peroxy radical (C7) are examined. Already after the initial addition of a benzoyl peroxy radical to the double bond of a monoterpene, a C17 compound is formed. We first estimated saturation vapor pressures for studied monoterpene+benzoyl peroxy radical+O₂ compounds using COSMOtherm. To ensure that the estimated values for the RO₂ intermediates are reliable, we also calculated saturation vapor pressures for the corresponding closed-shell systems (R-OOH) (see Figure 7). The results are shown in Table 4.

Based on the classification proposed by Donahue et al., (2012)²² the results indicate that compounds derived from α -pinene, β -pinene, and limonene can be classified as SVOCs, whereas the sabinene-derived intermediate already falls into the LVOC category. This is particularly important, as the low-volatility product is formed in a two-step reaction (one of which is the very fast O₂ addition). Following the approach of Hyttinen et al., (2024)⁹⁴ we adopt the 95% confidence intervals for the estimation of p_{sat} of 1.0 and 1.4 for the liquid and solid phases, respectively. These correspond roughly to an uncertainty of 1 order of magnitude in the saturation vapor pressures. Considering this uncertainty, if we assume an overestimation, the classification of the investigated compounds remains largely unchanged. If we assume underestimation, some compounds currently classified as SVOCs would fall near the boundary between the SVOC and LVOC, depending on the classification cutoff.

Figure 7. Closed-shell product structures of monoterpene + benzoyl peroxy radical-initiated oxidation, for which saturation vapor pressures were calculated using COSMO-therm and COSMO-ML.

Table 4. COSMO-ML-Predicted and COSMOtherm-Estimated Saturation Vapour Pressures (p_{sat} in Pa) of Monoterpene(mt) + Benzoyl Peroxy Radical Oxidation Products at 298.15 K^a

MT + $C_6H_5C(O)OO\cdot$	molecular formula	COSMO-ML, solid	COSMO-ML, liquid	COSMOtherm, liquid	classification
α -Pinene-1-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_5$	3.0×10^{-5}	5.5×10^{-4}	5.2×10^{-5}	SVOC
β -Pinene-1-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_5$	9.0×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-3}	2.6×10^{-5}	SVOC
Limonene-1-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_5$	1.6×10^{-6}	4.5×10^{-5}	2.6×10^{-5}	SVOC
Sabinene-1-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_5$	5.2×10^{-6}	1.5×10^{-4}	2.4×10^{-7}	LVOC
System					
Sabinene-RC0-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_6$	7.3×10^{-7}	7.4×10^{-6}	2.6×10^{-5}	SVOC/LVOC
Sabinene-IM4-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_8$	6.2×10^{-11}	1.3×10^{-10}	1.5×10^{-13}	ELVOC
Sabinene-RC2-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_5$	3.6×10^{-6}	8.1×10^{-5}	3.9×10^{-5}	SVOC
Sabinene-IM7-OOH	$C_{17}H_{22}O_7$	2.6×10^{-8}	1.7×10^{-7}	1.4×10^{-7}	LVOC

^aNote that the uncertainty in the saturation vapor pressures is approximately one order of magnitude.

Furthermore, we studied subsequent oxidation steps for sabinene-derived peroxy radicals to see how the next oxidation steps affect the vapor pressures of formed compounds. As indicated by the results in Table 4, the saturation vapor pressure depends not only on the number of oxygen atoms or molar mass, but heavily on the actual structure of the compound, as shown previously by, e.g., Barley and McFiggans (2010)¹⁰⁸ O'Meara et al. (2014),¹⁰⁹ and Kurtén et al. (2016).¹¹⁰ Interestingly, the estimated vapor pressure of the sabinene-RC0-OOH system is higher than that of sabinene-1-OOH, even though sabinene-RC0-OOH is a product of further oxidation of sabinene-1-OOH. Continued oxidation leads to the formation of the sabinene-IM4 intermediate, for which the estimated saturation vapor pressure is extremely low (1.5×10^{-13} Pa), indicating that this compound already qualifies as an ELVOC.

Moreover, we observe that the calculated vapor pressures for two sabinene-derived isomers ($C_{17}H_{22}O_5$) differ, indicating that the structural isomer of an intermediate influences the compound's volatility. The key structural difference between these two compounds is the presence of an additional ring in sabinene-1-OOH compared to sabinene-RC2-OOH. A lower vapor pressure was estimated for sabinene-1-OOH, which retains the bicyclic structure.

3.5. Atmospheric Significance and Limitations. This research provides insight into the acyl peroxy radical-initiated oxidation of monoterpenes. First, we studied the accretion reaction between four monoterpenes: α -pinene, β -pinene, limonene, and sabinene with benzoyl peroxy radical. We investigated all possible addition sites on the double bond and calculated the total reaction rate coefficient. The fastest reactions were observed for α -pinene (10^{-15} cm³/molecules s⁻¹) and limonene (10^{-15} cm³/molecules s⁻¹), which, compared to experimental values for OH-initiated oxidation, account for $\sim 1\%$ of the monoterpene sink. However, as discussed in the main text, our calculations may be underestimated, and experimental work is needed to fully understand the actual impact of these reactions. The authors expect the yield to be at most a few percent. That would imply minor but not negligible atmospheric significance and high relevance for chamber studies.

Furthermore, we continued work described in Pasik et al. (2025)⁸⁷ and investigated the APR-oxidation pathway of sabinene-derived radicals. Ultimately, the focus of this study was the benzoyl peroxy radical-derived systems, but because of the high computational cost, calculations were performed for sabinene + acetyl peroxy radical-derived systems, assuming that the benzoyl peroxy radical would react analogously. We showed the detailed mechanism of APR-initiated oxidation of

sabinene, which proceeds via unimolecular reactions. We found a novel branching point in the sabinene oxidation pathway: the opening of a 3-membered ring leading to the rapid autoxidation pathway (for the compound denoted as RC1). That was observed for both APR- and NO_3 -derived systems. This brings the general conclusion that if the radical center is placed on a carbon next to the 3-membered ring, a ring-opening reaction is very likely to happen. This unexplored mechanism leads rapidly to low-volatility compounds, which might explain the high SOA yield observed from sabinene oxidation.

Saturation vapor pressures of intermediates from $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$ -initiated oxidation were estimated using COSMO-therm. We found that the accretion reaction of monoterpene + $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$, followed by O_2 -addition produces low-volatility compounds, which can be classified as SVOCs (limonene, α -pinene, and β -pinene) or even LVOCs (sabinene). This implies that benzoyl peroxy radical-initiated oxidation can produce products capable of participating in aerosol processes, highlighting their great importance in the atmospheric context. Especially, the knowledge of saturation vapor pressures of SVOCs is crucial in climate modeling, as uncertainties in the representation of semivolatile compounds lead to the largest uncertainties in predicting the climate effects of aerosols.¹¹¹ Saturation vapor pressures of selected intermediates in sabinene oxidation were also estimated, one of which had vapor pressure that falls into ELVOCs regime. In addition, we observed that stereochemistry affects branching ratios between different oxidation pathways, leading to compounds with different volatilities. This implies that the volatility of a HOM is also related to the stereochemistry of the intermediates. Along with the reaction rate coefficients for MT + APR reported in this work, this reaction accounts for a maximum of 1% of the monoterpene oxidation sinks. While this oxidation is a minor pathway, it may play a surprisingly important role in the production of the lowest-volatility oxidation products via subsequent autoxidation. Recent work by Dada et al. (2023) showed that only highly oxygenated products with at least 15 carbon atoms are sufficiently low-volatile (ultralow-volatility organic compounds, ULVOC – saturation vapor pressure less than 10^{-14} Pa) to nucleate under atmospheric conditions.³⁰ As benzoyl peroxy radical oxidation leads directly to products with more than 15 carbon atoms, but OH-, NO_3 - or ozone- initiated oxidation leads to C10 products, the suggested MT + APR pathways might lead to oxidation products capable to nucleate. As in the case of MT + other oxidants, bimolecular $\text{RO}_2 + \text{RO}_2$ chemistry is needed to lead to > C15 compounds, the MT + benzoyl peroxy radical reaction might serve as an important source in the production of > C15 compounds capable of nucleating. In any case, the direct comparison of these pathways and their relative importance is not straightforward.

In this study, the reaction of APRs with monoterpenes was examined; however, other compounds containing double bonds are expected to react in the same way. Thus, this might be of high relevance in polluted areas, where various chemicals are emitted from human activities. On the other hand, these reactions would have the biggest impact in low NO_x concentration areas, because of the main sink of APR is its reaction with NO_2 .^{4,61} Recent studies by Newland et al. (2021)¹¹² reported the formation of gas- and aerosol-phase oxidation products typically associated with “low- NO_x ” atmospheric pathways during the afternoon in Beijing, China,

driven by the pronounced suppression of NO concentrations at that time of day. Typically, large cities with heavy traffic, industrial activity, and other emission sources experience elevated air pollution levels and are generally considered to represent high- NO_x conditions. However, studies have shown that in the afternoon, NO_x concentrations can drop to around 1 ppb.¹¹² Such conditions—characterized by high emissions of various pollutants but simultaneously low NO_x levels—are particularly relevant for the reactions proposed in this work.

Moreover, the reaction between benzoyl peroxy radicals and monoterpenes can be significant for indoor air chemistry. Benzaldehyde has been detected at relatively high concentrations (0.65 ± 0.42 ppb) in residential indoor air, as reported by Jurvelin et al. (2003).⁵⁶ At the same time, monoterpenes are widely emitted from numerous indoor sources.¹¹³ Among them, limonene is the most abundant, with concentrations strongly influenced by household products such as cleaning agents and air fresheners.¹¹⁴ In addition, limonene is naturally present in citrus fruits. Król et al. (2014)¹¹³ measured levels of selected monoterpenes in indoor air and found limonene to be the most abundant, with average concentrations of $350 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (~ 62 ppb) and up to $1200 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (~ 215 ppb). These overlapping emission sources (combined with low- NO_x levels) create conditions where benzoyl peroxy radical–monoterpene chemistry may be particularly relevant indoors.

As emphasized in previous sections, there are many unknowns related to the benzoyl peroxy radical-initiated oxidation of monoterpenes. Reactions between peroxy radicals and double bonds were the focus of experimental studies by Nozière et al.^{63,106} For reactions with $\text{CH}_3\text{C}(\text{O})\text{OO}\cdot$, they reported rate coefficients on the order of $\sim 10^{-14}$ molecules/ cm^3/s . Even though the reaction rate of $\text{RO}_2 + \text{isoprene}$ is relatively small, it can significantly reduce the total RO_2 concentration by 10–50%, as described in Nozière et al. (2021).¹⁰⁶ This occurs because $\text{RO}_2 + \text{isoprene}$ competes with fast unimolecular sinks, which efficiently recycle OH and largely control OH levels. As a result, even minor $\text{RO}_2 + \text{alkene}$ reactions can strongly influence OH recycling, isoprene oxidation, and overall RO_2 production, making their impact larger than that expected from their low reaction rates.

This highlights the need for further research in this direction. We expect the proposed reactions of acyl peroxy radicals with alkenes to have a rather local but still important impact on SOA formation. Field measurements are needed to quantify the contribution of APR + monoterpenes under real atmospheric conditions and to assess their implications for air quality and climate.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

The optimized structures and calculation output files of all relevant compounds that support the findings of the paper are available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17668927>.

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.est.5c14072>.

Supporting Information. S1: β -scission reaction rates; S2: tunneling coefficient for IM7 H-shift-3; S3: H-shifts sabinene-IM2l; S4: saturation vapor pressures; S5: alkyl radical ring-opening reactions for sabinene- NO_3 -derived systems; S6: Lennard-Jones parameters for RRKM-ME

calculations; S7: addition of $C_6H_5C(O)OO$. to double bond in monoterpenes; S8: estimation of $C_6H_5C(O)OO$. concentration in the atmosphere; and S9: APR +MT reaction energetics (PDF)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Dominika Pasik – Department of Chemistry, University of Helsinki, Helsinki 00014, Finland; Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research, University of Helsinki, Helsinki 00014, Finland; orcid.org/0009-0009-3304-5495;
Email: dominika.pasik@helsinki.fi

Nanna Myllys – Department of Chemistry, University of Helsinki, Helsinki 00014, Finland; Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research, University of Helsinki, Helsinki 00014, Finland; orcid.org/0000-0003-0384-7277;
Email: nanna.myllys@helsinki.fi

Authors

Noora Hyttinen – Atmospheric Research Centre of Eastern Finland, Finnish Meteorological Institute, Kuopio 70211, Finland; orcid.org/0000-0002-6025-5959

Siddharth Iyer – Aerosol Physics Laboratory, Tampere University, Tampere 33014, Finland; orcid.org/0000-0001-5989-609X

Complete contact information is available at:
<https://pubs.acs.org/10.1021/acs.est.5c14072>

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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